

PHRASEOLOGY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN THE UZBEK SCHOOL

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Summary: In the article, on the example of adverbial phraseological units with the meaning “space” and “quantity”, the features of studying and enriching the speech of Uzbek students with phraseological units of the Russian language are considered.

Key words: phraseology, linguoculturology, intercultural communication, cognitive linguistics, integral seme, semantic structure.

Introduction.

Phraseology in the school course of Russian as a foreign language contains a huge educational, developmental and educational potential. From the point of view of linguoculturology, the study and enrichment of the speech of Uzbek students with phraseological units of the Russian language makes it possible to familiarize them with Russian culture, develop their language reserve, and largely weaken the influence of the interference of their native language. “Phraseological units, reflecting in their semantics a long process of development of the culture of the people, fix and transmit cultural attitudes and stereotypes from generation to generation... This is the soul of any national language, in which the spirit and originality of the nation are expressed in a unique way. It is not easy for a teacher of Russian as a foreign language from the first time after students read a certain text to give an idea of what is said in the text, which includes a number of phraseological turns, without preliminary dictionary work. The process of studying Russian phraseology by Uzbek students requires thoughtful and purposeful work. The teacher needs to correctly select the input language phraseological units. The material should be relevant, actively used in the speech of native speakers of the language being studied, contain an ethnic and cultural component and be thematically organized.

As the analysis of modern programs and textbooks shows, the teaching of the Russian language in schools with the Uzbek language of instruction is gradually, but purposefully moving to a content basis. Grammar and vocabulary of the Russian language are presented to students not as a set of formal classifications, but as a means that primarily serves to formalize the content and establishes links between linguistic units within words, phrases and sentences.

Practical knowledge of a foreign language involves (in addition to the active assimilation of vocabulary and grammatical structures) the use of phraseological units. In this regard, the mastery of a certain part of the phraseological material by students, which contains a very significant part of the expressive language fund, which serves as an effective source of sustainable communication skills, acquires great attention in this regard.

Purpose of the study

One of the important problems in the study of phraseological units is the implementation of their translation, which is associated with such areas of linguistics as linguoculturology, intercultural

communication, cognitive linguistics, as well as methodological aspects. On the one hand, in order to master the Russian language perfectly, it is necessary to have an idea of the Russian language picture of the world, where an important element is knowledge of the phraseology of the Russian language. On the other hand, knowledge and understanding of phraseological units is a kind of criterion for the degree of knowledge of the Russian language.

Since the Russian and Uzbek languages belong to different language families, and there is a discrepancy between their structures, it becomes necessary to use educational translation in teaching the Russian language in the Uzbek school. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the data of a comparative analysis of the phraseological systems of both languages.

Materials and research methods

When studying phraseological units, it is most effective to use an equivalent translation based on their semantic analysis. For example, let's conduct a comparative analysis of adverbial phraseological units-antonyms with the meaning "space" and "quantity".

Results and its discussion

The semantic composition of NPU with the meaning "space" of the Russian and Uzbek languages has the following form:

1. PU with the meaning "length in space".

1) NPU with the integral seme "location" express the different location of objects (in a broad sense) in relation to the subject of the action in terms of their close or distant location. Consequently, all phraseological units with the indicated meaning, depending on the expressed or semantics, can be divided into two parts that are in a state of opposition to each other.

a) NPU with the seme of the real meaning "close" indicate that some action or object is located or performed at a small distance from the subject: *pod samim nosom, rukoy podat, v dvux shagax, odin shag; ko'z o'ngida, yaqin o'rtada, qo'l cho'zsa yetkudek, ikki qadamda; under the very nose, at hand, two steps away, one step, etc.* The semantic structure of this kind of PU contains the seme "close".

In addition, in the Russian language there are still a number of units indicating a close location: *side by side, yard by yard, nose to nose, shoulder to shoulder, etc.* As can be inferred from the above examples, they indicate a very close location of two living beings (usually people). A more accurate semantic seme for this kind of PU would be "nearby".

b) NPU with the seme of the real meaning "far" indicate that the action or object, respectively, takes place or is located at a considerable distance, at a great distance from the object of the action: *za tri devyat zemel, u cherta na kulichkax, ne blijniy svet, kuda Makar telyat ne gonyal; dunyoning bir chetida, inson oyog'i bosmagan joyda, bir chaqirimdan; for three nine lands, in the middle of nowhere, not a passing light, where Makar did not drive calves, etc.*

2) Adverbial phraseological units with the integral seme "location" are associated with the designation of the location of one or another object, person.

a) NPU with the seme of real meaning "everywhere" are used to express a different location, that is, they indicate that an object (in the broad sense) is everywhere, everywhere and everywhere on

a vast territory: *iz kontsa v konets, po belu svetu, naskolko xvataet glaz, splosh i ryadom; xar qadamda, odim joyda, gir aylana; from end to end, across the wide world, as far as the eye can see, all the time*, etc.

b) Phraseological units with the seme of the real meaning "nowhere" act with the opposite meaning to the units considered above in the subgroup under study: *ochiq mozorda, hech jahonda, yetti iqlimda, ikki olamda; in an open grave, in no world, in seven climes, in two worlds*, etc.

2. Adverbial phraseological units with the meaning "orientation in space".

a) Basically, units with similar semantics indicate a different direction of action or movement: *vdol i poperek, kto kuda, na vse chetire storoni, vokrug do okolo; boshi oqqan tomonga, o' burchakdan bu burchakka; up and down, who goes where, on all four sides, around to about*, etc. The seme of the real value for the indicated type of units is "in different directions".

b) NPU with a seme of real meaning "in none of the directions": *ni vzad ni vpered* and *na u yoqqa na bu yoqqa*, and *neither back nor forth*. These units indicate that some action is impossible in any of the possible directions.

Quantitative phraseological units include such units as: *polon rot, schetu net, kak iz roga izobiliya, rovnim schetom, kak na Malaninu svadbu, xot otbavlyay, raz-dva i obchelsya, kaplya v more; maymun yemaydi, burnidan chiqquncha, bir bahya, to'rt g'giz, nari borsa, boshga bosh, tanga tashlasa yerga tushmaydi, sahabalarning uyiday; the mouth is full, there is no count, as if from a cornucopia, absolutely, like at Malanin's wedding, more than enough, one or two and miscalculated, a drop in the ocean*, etc.

Phraseologisms of this kind do not express their own quantitative meaning, do not have an exact numerical measurement (with the exception of one unit in the Russian language, a *chertova dyujina; damn dozen* - "thirteen"). They only denote an indefinite number, which can be in a huge or negligible amount, and in some cases indicate its complete absence. Therefore, we divided the main part of the units of the type under consideration into two large groups that are in opposition to each other, having the following form: "a lot" - "few".

1. Phraseologisms included in this group express a very large number, countless number of something or someone: *net otboya, xot prud prudi, kak iz roga izobiliya, kuri ne klyuyut, tolko ptichego moloka ne xvataet, do Moskvi ne pereveshaesh; bir qop, bir tuda, bir gala, qirg'izga yetadi, son mingta, yerdan osmongacha, tanga tashlasa yerga tushmaydi, sen ye men ye; there is no end, even a dime a dozen, as if from a cornucopia, chickens do not peck, only there is not enough bird's milk, you can't outweigh it to Moscow*, etc. Despite the diverse external grammatical structure, in all the given examples there is a common element of meaning for them - the integrating seme "a lot", which is present in the semantic structure of each of the phraseological units introduced here.

On the other hand, the presence of a common seme does not mean that they are in a synonymous relationship with each other. In order for them to be in synonymous relations with each other, one should take into account the meaning of the words with which they are in close semantic and syntactic connection. In other words, the commonality of the expressed meaning of words

combined with phraseological units is the indispensable condition that allows us to consider them synonyms.

So, in this group, several synonymous rows can be distinguished, where, firstly, phraseological units that are close in meaning and, secondly, units with the same distribution are introduced. For example:

a) phraseological units denoting the complete abundance of products, edibles, various food: *yesh ne xochu, kak na Malaninu svadbu, tolko ptichego moloka ne xvataet, skolko dushe ugodno, razlivannoe more - bir dunyo, qirg'izga yetadi, maymun yemaydi, sen ye men ye, burnidan chiqquncha; I don't want to eat, like at Malany's wedding, only there's not enough bird's milk, as much as you like, a spilled sea, etc.*

b) phraseological units denoting a large amount of money: *det nekuda, kuri ne klyuyut, beda skolko, chertova propast - bijib yotibdi, oshib-toshib yotibdi, shundan shuncha; nowhere to go, chickens do not peck, the trouble is how much, damn abyss, etc.*

c) phraseological units denoting a huge number of people, living beings: *pushkoy ne proshibesh, odin na drugom sedit, net otboya, do Moskvi ne pereveshaesh, kak seldey v bochke - bir gala, bir etak, sakson foiz, sanog'i yo'q, qalashib yotibdi, son mingta; you can't break through with a cannon, one sits on top of the other, there's no lights out, you can't hang it to Moscow, like a herring in a barrel, etc.*

d) phraseological units denoting a large number in combination with verbs of speaking (speech) that have a negative emotional connotation: *s tri koroba, sem verst do nebes - bir jahon, bir qop, bir vagon, ellik og'iz; from three boxes, seven miles to heaven, etc.*

It should be noted that individual phraseological units included in this microsystem may participate in different subgroups. So, units of the type: *beda skolko, chertova propast, xot prud prudi, kak pesku morskogo; sanog'i yo'q, bijib yotibdi, son mingta, qalashib yotibdi; the trouble is how much, the damn abyss, even a dime a dozen, like the sand of the sea* and some others can indicate both a large number of people and objects in the broad sense of the word, that is, they have wide compatibility possibilities, which allows them to participate in different synonymous series.

2. Phraseological units assigned to this group are realized in speech with the meaning of an indefinitely small amount. Depending on the semantics they designate, they can be combined into two microgroups:

a) phraseological units expressing an extremely small amount of something or someone (integrating seme - "very little"): *s gulkin nos, po paltsam mojno pereschitat, raz-dva i obchelsya, kot naplakal, na odin zub - tutantiriq ham bo'lmaydi, urug'liqqa ham yo'q, barmoq bilan sanarli, daryodan bir tomchi, pichoqning sirticha; with a gulkin nose, you can count on the fingers, one or two and miscalculated, the cat cried, for one tooth, etc.*

b) phraseological units indicating an insufficient, insignificant amount of something or someone (integrating seme - "a little"): *ne axti skolko, maluyu toliku, malim delom, detishkam na molochishko - bir chimdim, bir tishlam, bir cho'qim, bir shingil, bir og'iz, bir fasl, bir bahya, bir go'ltim; not so hot how much, a small fraction, a small deed, the kids for milk, etc.*

The phraseological units presented in the first group are opposed to the units of this group. However, the opposition of the concepts expressed by them does not yet give us grounds to consider them antonyms. The condition for establishing antonymic relations between the units we are considering is the commonality, the identity of the words with which these phraseological units enter into compatibility relations. So, for example, phraseological units indicating a complete abundance of products are antonymized with units of the type: *na odin zub, kuram na smex, kak slonu drobina – chap ichakka ham yuq bo'lmaydi, urvoq ham bo'lmaydi*; for one tooth, for chickens to laugh, like a pellet for an elephant; and phraseological units expressing a large amount of money act as antonyms in relation to units of the type: *kot naplakal, maluyu toliku, kaplya v more – daryodan bir tomchi, o'tdan bir uchqun; the cat cried, a small fraction, a drop in the ocean, etc.*

3. This includes phraseological units that indicate the absence of any quantity. The impossibility of numerical measurement in both languages is carried out, as a rule, in relation to objects (in the broad sense): *ni v zub nogoy, ni makovoy rosinki, s pustimi rukami, xot sharom pokati, ni sin poroxa, rojki da nojki, ni kola ni dvora; qoq yer qora ship, quruq qo'l bilan, quruqdan quruq, sahobalarning uyiday, ikki qo'lini burniga tiqib; neither a tooth with a foot, nor a poppy dew, with empty hands, even a rolling ball, no blue gunpowder, horns and legs, no stake or yard, etc.* A single semantic element that allows uniting the above units into one microsystem is the presence in the semantic structure of each of them of the integrating seme "not at all" (or "nothing").

4. This group is represented by one phraseological unit in Russian, and several in Uzbek, which simultaneously contain an indication of both a large number and a small one: *nevest skolko; bir talay, bir hovuch, bir siqim; who knows how many*. Let's compare: *Vodi bilo nevest skolko, no vse je napit'sya bilo nevozmojno (iz razgovornoy rechi) i Mi tratim ...luchshie minuti, kak budto ix i nevest skolko v zapase. (Herzen. Past and thoughts); O'lis yo'lga o'tlangan sayyohlar ham Mingbuloqda to'htab, devziradan bir siqim osh qilib yeb ketishmasa kungillari joyiga tushmasdi (U.Umarbekov. It's hard to be human, p.8) – Bir siqim qizil suvorilar ularning qoq biqinidan yorib kirib qilich tig'ining kuchini ko'rsatmoqdalar (S.Azimov. Song of the White Dawn, p. 308). There was God knows how much water, but it was still impossible to get drunk (from colloquial speech) and We spend ... the best minutes, as if there were God knows how many of them in stock.*

5. Phraseologisms included in this group do not express their own quantitative meaning. They serve to express delimitation, the separation of a specific number of objects (in the broad sense) from a multitude of similar ones. Such units, used in combination with numerals, denote a certain amount: *rovnim schetom, kak odnu kopeyku, vsego navsego, po menshey mere – juda bo'lsa, nari borsa, aylantirib kelganda, yo'q deganda; exactly, like one penny, just, at least, etc.*

6. The last group includes units that indicate the proportionality of the action: *tak na tak, bash na bash, stenka na stenku, odin na odin; boshga bosh, birga bir; so on so, bash to bash, wall to wall, one to one, etc.*

Conclusions.

The phraseological system of the Russian language is widely represented by units with the meaning of "space" and "quantity". An in-depth study of these phraseosemantic groups makes it possible to identify not only their most diverse semantic shades, but also helps to warn students against possible mistakes when using them in speech. Taking into account the above semantic correspondences of the NPU of the Russian and Uzbek languages with the meaning "space" and "quantity" when teaching Russian as a foreign language can be an effective means of enriching the vocabulary of students and neutralizing the negative impact of the interference of the Uzbek and Russian languages.

The study of phraseological units in the lessons of Russian as a foreign language is of great importance in the formation of the communicative competence of students in Uzbek schools: students' knowledge of the vocabulary of the Russian language is significantly improved, their oral speech develops, and their vocabulary is enriched. Students better and deeper understand Russian literary texts, learn to make their correct linguistic analysis. And in general, when using phraseological units, students' speech becomes more vivid, correct and stylistically colored.

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